

DTO-BioFlow

Integration of biodiversity monitoring
data into the Digital Twin Ocean

dto-bioflow.eu

Marine Biodiversity Data Barriers in Europe: *A practical guide*

How DTO-BioFlow is
overcoming challenges to
sustain marine biodiversity
through data innovation

Funded by
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Europe's seas need **help**. How **technology** came to rescue.

*Europe's marine ecosystems are among the richest in the world but face threats from climate change, pollution, overfishing, and habitat loss. To effectively protect and manage these ecosystems, access to high-quality marine biodiversity data is essential.

However, several barriers prevent the seamless flow of this data. Discover how the DTO-BioFlow project is seeking to overcome these barriers by integrating diverse marine biodiversity datasets into the **EU Digital Twin of the Ocean (EU DTO)** contributing to provide more accurate information for better marine management.

*This information is based on the deliverable Deliverable D2.2 - Barriers Playbook

What are the **main barriers** and specific obstacles **that are most challenging in enabling data** to flow into the pathways developed within the DTO-BioFlow project?

Barriers identified by DTO-BioFlow fall into a handful of categories: resources, technical, legal, governance, and cultural.

Resources

Many data providers lack the funding and resources to continuously maintain and share their data, resulting in gaps in data availability.

Technical

Data is often stored in incompatible formats, preventing smooth integration into global and regional databases like the EU Digital Twin of the Ocean (EU DTO).

Cultural

There is a lack of collaboration between different sectors and countries, resulting in fragmented data silos. Without clear communication and trust, sharing information is limited.

Governance

Different data owners and organizations have varying policies on how data are accessed, shared, and used, leading to inconsistent practices.

Legal

There is a lack of clear legal frameworks and complex legal restrictions, including intellectual property rights, that complicate the sharing of marine biodiversity data, particularly across borders.

These obstacles hinder effective marine policy implementation and environmental management.

Which types of **data require the most effort** when trying to on board to the European Digital Twin of the Ocean (EU DTO)?

The DTO-BioFlow project has a specific focus on data flows that are not as mature as well-established marine biodiversity data flows in Europe and includes:

Genomic Data (eDNA - Environmental DNA)

Genomic data, such as DNA sequences collected from environmental samples, is one of the most challenging to onboard. The difficulties arise from the need for standardized formats and the infrastructure required to manage and process large volumes of genetic data.

Plankton Imaging

Plankton imaging data, collected through advanced imaging technologies, is another data type that presents significant challenges. The issue lies in the complexity of image data processing, the lack of standardization in image formats, and the need for accurate taxonomic classification.

Biologging Data (Animal Tracking)

Data from biologging, which tracks the movements and behaviors of marine animals (such as fish, mammals, and birds), is also challenging to integrate. This data are often diverse, collected through different devices and sensors, and require specific formats and consistent taxonomic identification for it to be usable in the EU DTO.

Cetacean Passive Acoustic Monitoring

Data collected through passive acoustic monitoring of cetaceans (whales, dolphins, etc.) present technical difficulties due to issues with data standardization, the complexity of audio data processing, and the need for appropriate context (e.g., species identification, environmental context). This type of data requires a standardized pipeline to be useful in the EU DTO.

Data from Existing Observation Networks

Although not necessarily "new," some existing marine biodiversity data, such as cetacean and seabird datasets, face challenges in being integrated into the EU DTO. These data are often stored in localized or national databases and require significant data transformation to meet EU DTO standards.

Looking Ahead

The Barriers Playbook

DTO-BioFlow is working on a comprehensive Barriers Playbook that will provide practical guidance on overcoming the most significant data access challenges.

Scheduled for release in Autumn 2026, this playbook will offer:

Technical Solutions

Step-by-step guides for overcoming technical issues related to data formats, integration tools, and automation.

Governance Models

Real-world examples and recommendations for improving collaboration, data sharing agreements, and regulatory frameworks.

Case Studies

Insights from the project's data flows, including challenges faced and lessons learned from the Genomics, Plankton Imaging, Biologging, and Cetacean Passive Acoustics pathways.

End-to-End Approaches

Holistic strategies for data management from collection to integration, ensuring long-term sustainability of data flows into the EU Digital Twin of the Ocean (EU DTO).

This playbook will serve as a practical, accessible resource for overcoming marine biodiversity data barriers across Europe.

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